

HOAX INTERNET BUSINESS: CASE STUDY OF HOAX CONTENT ON FACEBOOK

Author: Rissa Grace

Abstract:

It is said that a fool is born every minute. This is none more accurate than in Internet business hoaxes especially when you consider that the Internet reaches out to millions of people, provides for anonymity for everybody and allows for easy escapes for scammers. So, if you are to ask if online business hoaxes are fact or fiction, the answer is "Yes, it is fact!". However, just because it is a fact of life does not necessarily mean that you cannot avoid it. As with most facts of life, you have the choice to ensure that you will not form part of the statistics of fools born to fall prey to online business hoaxes. You just need to beware of the following promises, phrases and persons although it must be emphasized that with the numerous ways Internet business hoaxes disguise themselves, this list is definitely not all-inclusive.

Keyword: Hoax; Facebook; Culture; Hate Speech; Industry;

Introduction

Promises

Of course, there will be promises and as with most promises of money, you will be disappointed with the non-delivery. You should be very, very wary of promises regarding quick profits with little effort, of promises of insider information on the secrets to making quick money and of promises to provide a comfortable income if you buy into the product now.

These promises feed on your innate feelings of greed for wealth, pride in riches and lust for money, thus, the pressure brought upon you to invest now even before you have the opportunity to investigate further. Instead, you should look into business opportunities that allow you to think through your choices, that provide for decent income with decent work as a basis and that make no promises beyond what it can

deliver. Think along the lines of Internet marketing, which definitely cannot be counted as one of the Internet business hoaxes.

Discussion

Phrases

Beware of words to these effects:

- Guaranteed return on investment, high returns, risk free, work free - No investment, no business profits and no riches come with zero risks and zero work.
- Refer to companies looking for home workers for a fee - You will be provided with a generic, outdated and even non-existent list of companies that are unaware of the scam.
- Call our toll-free hotline numbers - This is how scammers earn money by making others call a hotline for more information.

Again, it is always better to search out Internet marketing job offers that require decent work in exchange for decent money. Of course, you will not get rich quick but you will get your money!

Persons

This is probably the hardest aspect of Internet business hoaxes to detect. After all, aliases and pseudonyms are as common as sand on the beach with scammers. Indeed, knowing who is who online can be difficult but not impossible. You can usually detect the same person using different aliases when the style of writing, the sites frequented and the aliases used are similar. Or better yet, you should ask for complete names and addresses of the persons behind the offers.

Facebook - Hoaxes and Spam

We are seeing more and more people falling prey to what appears to be Facebook Hoaxes, spam and scams. The one currently circulating in Australia is the "Graph Search App", well if your reading this post chances are you also know about

graph Search as its something i have a strong belief in. The "Graph search App" hoax isn't really true, graph is not an app, quite simply its the database within Facebook.

I try to make comment on peoples posts about the hoax, yet they continue to spread it? Why? I have no idea! Intelligent people spreading what is clearly a hoax. Yet not one person have ever asked why is it a hoax and what does the perpetrator gain or achieve by someone copying and pasting a post? Not one Person has asked that question; they just follow like sheep and obey the instructions, then complain later.

So what's in it for the perpetrator of such a hoax? There are many types of these things on Facebook, either via an App, an image or simply a post, like the one we are talking about now. The App ones are easy to work out as they ask for permission; you are then on a mailing list, simple.

Images are used to create viral content, hence the spreading (and also a part of any Facebook marketing, read my eBook for more on that).

But the post type Hoax appears to have absolutely no value to anyone? Well there is value, these types of Hoax have nicknames "friendly hacks", there is no real nastiness going on, just ego and satisfaction for putting it out and tricking a few people along the way.

However, there is also a benefit; Edgerank; Edgerank is what Facebook uses (its algorithm) to decide if a post, or users, value in Facebook; in short the more engagement (That is after all the purpose of Social Media) then the higher your Edgerank will be.

Therefore, spreading such posts will no doubt aid the user to gain more Facebook traction, and yes that also helps those passing it on. Ironically, this passing on the hoaxes are actually often concerned about their privacy, yet all they are doing is assisting in creating a higher Edgerank to actually cut privacy. lol

In a nut shell, there is only one Privacy setting you need to know "If its private don't post it!" Simple really. Don't forget, Facebook is Social Media, not Private Media. So in short, just be social.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Internet business hoaxes do exist in this world. The question of whether you are going to fall for these hoaxes remains in your hands. You can become a fool or you can become a wise businessman. If you choose the latter, then we suggest you go for reputable Internet marketing but that's for another day.

References

- Badjatiya, P., Gupta, S., Gupta, M., & Varma, V. (2017, April). Deep learning for hate speech detection in tweets. In *Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on World Wide Web Companion* (pp. 759-760). International World Wide Web Conferences Steering Committee.
- Farhan, R. (2019). Understanding Postmodernism: Philosophy and Culture of Postmodern. Unpublished. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33590.04165>
- Habibi, H. (2018). PROTECTING NATIONAL IDENTITY BASED ON THE VALUE OF NATION LOCAL WISDOM. *International Journal of Malay-Nusantara Studies*, 1(2), 24-40.
- Jason, R. (2019). The Culture of Narcissism: Cultural Dilemmas, Language Confusion and The Formation of Social Identity. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Education Research*, 4(2), 01-19.
- Maya, L. (2019, December 24). GLOBALIZATION: A MIXTURE OF CULTURES AND DISADVANTAGING DEVELOPING COUNTRIES. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/3rpf6>
- Rahayu, W. H., Utari, P., & Wijaya, M. (2019). The Motivation of Hoax Message Recipients in the Process of Disseminating Hoax Information on Facebook Group. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 6(4), 414-421.
- Rangkuti, R., Pratama, A., & Zulfan, Z. (2019). HATE SPEECH ACTS: A CASE IN BATU BARA. *Language Literacy: Journal of Linguistics, Literature, and Language Teaching*, 3(2), 225-233.
- Rex, E. (2019). Understand Cross-Cultural Analysis. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/wtg3x>
- Sellnow, T. L., Parrish, A., & Semenas, L. (2019). From Hoax as Crisis to Crisis as Hoax: Fake News and Information Disorder as Disruptions to the Discourse of Renewal. *Journal of International Crisis and Risk Communication Research*, 2(1), 6.
- Waldron, J. (2012). *The harm in hate speech*. Harvard University Press.
- Walker, S. (1994). *Hate speech: The history of an American controversy*. U of Nebraska Press.

